

LANGUAGE IS THE MIRROR OF A NATION

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Abstract: A country's spiritual richness and image are reflected in its language. Language is a tool for communication, but it also conveys a country's culture, history, way of life, and customs. Respect for diverse languages thus fosters communication and understanding between people.

Language is a property and a symbol of the state. The nation will rise as long as the language is preserved and developed. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan legally enshrines the status of the state language. Stated differently, our national language, like our flag, coat of arms, and national anthem, represents a sacred state that is legally protected. The ability to communicate through language is a priceless gift from the Creator to humanity. Language is one of the key characteristics that sets nations apart from one another. Every country in the world views its language as its greatest asset, source of pride, and means of salvation.

Poetry, epics, songs, and wise words all originate in a country's original tongue. A nation's language will endure for as long as it does, and during that time it will maintain its unique status among other languages. Each country speaks its own language. Russian was established as the official language of the Union during the Soviet era. It is now on par with other world languages. With a long and rich history, the Turkic peoples in particular have maintained that their mother tongue is just as valuable as any other language on the planet. They disregarded the man-made obstacles lining the path. It was not in vain that proposals and efforts were made to elevate Uzbek, which had descended to the status of a family and market language on the eve of independence, to the status of the state language. The

designation of Uzbek as the official language has been granted. Books, magazines, and official documents started to be written in our mother tongue. It has raised our people's morale. The goal to revive Uzbek and establish it as the official language was strong even during the Soviet era. Attempts to host different occasions honoring the mother tongue in particular have increased, particularly in the run-up to independence. The Language Festival, a new holiday, first made headlines in 1988. The holiday has reportedly been observed in the capital, the Baltic and Transcaucasian republics, the Russian Federation, and Ukraine, according to newspapers. These festivities were primarily intended to honor mother tongues and inspire students to acquire additional languages in addition to their mother tongue.

We commemorate October 21 of each year as the day the Uzbek language became the official state language. The festival is held under a new slogan every year. These include sayings like "Language is the mirror of the nation," "Mother tongue is my soul," and "Attention to the language is attention to the people." The depth of each school teacher's profession and their level of intelligence determine the meaning and enjoyment of the language festival. To the language festival are invited linguists, literary scholars, poets, and well-known authors. They instill in the youth the belief that learning a language is essential for success, that one should cherish one's mother tongue, and that learning foreign languages should come first. Festivals dedicated to language often include proverbs, poetry, and musical compositions. There will be entertaining shows on radio and television on this day dedicated to the language holiday. Language Day is a special occasion that encourages people to cherish their native tongue and their community. Another significant element in fostering intercultural peace and friendship is Language Day. The Uzbek language has gained prominence, attention, and the status of the state language—one of the biggest benefits and opportunities of the independence era. The Uzbek language is still a key component of our national identity and one of the primary markers of our independence to this day. Since no language has ever been fully studied and there is always more to learn about it, every principle of language

has equal importance and needs to be studied. Learning about the cognitive underpinnings of language acquisition and classification particularly interests me. Given the incredible discoveries that have been made thus far, I believe that the brain and its relationship to language will be the primary focus of research in the coming years. Additionally, neurolinguistics is a relatively unexplored field. The brain is a mystery, and there are a lot of unsolved questions when we examine it with words. Thus, linguists must investigate how humans understand language, communicate, and acquire grammar. It is not surprising that as technology advances, we will comprehend the nature of these phenomena better in the years to come.

Nowadays, there is consensus among linguists that language knowledge is an abstract concept. Rather than being familiar with particular sounds, words, or sentences, this type of knowledge is the understanding of the rules, conventions, and techniques surrounding pronunciation and the use of sounds. It involves understanding what should be said and what shouldn't be said, as well as what is and is not relevant to the language. It clarifies how we interpret new sentences and demonstrates how some people can refuse to accept that they are grammatically incorrect. When people understand each other, they can converse in a single language, but it can be challenging to comprehend how well they grasp the language. Genetic, social, and psychological variables undoubtedly play a significant part in this. In addition to being a common object, language also has an abstract meaning. People can always use language and communicate in appropriate ways. It is evident that the term "proper use" encompasses a broad range of abilities and behaviors.

The deliberate contribution of our intellectuals to the evolution of language, as well as the ongoing focus on and demand for literary standards, speech culture, and speech etiquette, are among the most significant tasks of our day. There are still places where words from other languages are misused. You can hear dialects and illogical sentences that defy literary conventions and style on the radio, television,

newspapers, and magazines. These are expressions of disinterest in our national culture and language. Every nation's language is its greatest asset, most valuable possession, heart, and voice. Internationalism is demonstrated by the fact that residents of Uzbekistan of different nationalities and ethnic groups learn Uzbek, interact with locals in this language, and respect the nation's culture, customs, and traditions as well as its rulers. Every nation's language is its greatest asset, most valuable possession, heart, and voice.

Internationalism is demonstrated by the fact that residents of Uzbekistan of different nationalities and ethnic groups learn Uzbek, interact with locals in this language, and respect the nation's culture, customs, and traditions as well as its rulers. A nation's language is its essence, its national-spiritual image, its psyche. The nation's image and spirit are its body and soul, and as such, they require constant care.

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